

Paper 6

Comparison of Private Universities in India based on NIRF Ranking and Fee Charging Strategies

P. S. Aithal^{*}, Madhushree^{**}, Revathi R.^{**}

^{*}Srinivas Institute of Management Studies, Srinivas University, Mangalore – 575 001, INDIA

E-mail : psaithal@gmail.com

^{**}Research Scholar, Srinivas Institute of Management Studies, Srinivas University,
Mangalore – India

Abstract

The need of additional universities in Indian higher education system to provide higher education to all eligible population of the country and the success of private university model in the USA tempted the Indian government to give permission to establish Private Universities in the country. Accordingly, based on section 22 of UGC act, the Indian government has allowed the state governments to establish private universities in the respective states. Presently there are 264 private universities in the country spread over 22 states. Due to non-availability of any financial support from the state and central governments, private universities are trying to sustain through their only strategy of service differentiation through 21st century curriculum and industry integrated programme design. In this paper, we have studied and compared some of the private universities in India in terms of their infrastructure, faculties, variety of courses, and fee structure of identified courses. We have also studied the performance scores given by NIRF, MHRD, Govt. of India for various criteria like Teaching, Learning & Resources, Research and Professional Practice, Graduation Outcomes, Outreach and Inclusivity, Public Perception. Based on the annual fee charged by the private universities established before 2010, we have identified three types of strategies which include low-fee – low quality, high-fee – high-quality, and low-fee – high quality strategies and analysed them based on the philosophy and background of such universities in general. We have also identified other innovative strategies offered by many private universities, in general, to differentiate themselves from publicly funded universities. The paper also contains some recommendations based on the observations to improve the quality, relevancy, and effectiveness of educational services and research contributions of private universities.

Keywords: Private universities, Business strategies, Growth strategies, Education service differentiation strategy, Innovations & best practices in higher education and research, Recommendations for private universities.

1. Introduction

Private universities are contributing to the higher education in many countries and in the United States they have acquired the top university status. As per the recent university ranking in the USA all top ten universities are private universities and sixteen universities out of twenty top US universities are private Universities as shown in Table 1. Based on the survey during last several years in the USA, all top ten Universities are from Private universities list and currently, only four Public universities have found a place out of Top twenty U.S. Universities [1]. The success of the private university model in the USA led to many countries to do similar experiments in higher education in their countries.

Table 1 : First twenty Top Universities in USA as per 2017-18 US University Ranking [1]

S. No	University	Type	World Ranking	USA Ranking	Location
1	Massachusetts Institute of Technology	Private	01	01	Cambridge, MA
2	Stanford University	Private	02	02	CA Stanford,
3	Harvard University	Private	03	03	Cambridge, MA
4	California Institute of Technology	Private	04	04	Pasadena, CA
5	University of Chicago	Private	09	05	Chicago, IL
6	Princeton University	Private	13	06	Princeton, NJ
7	Cornell University	Private	14	07	Ithaca, NY
8	Yale University	Private	16	08	New Haven, CT
9	Johns Hopkins University	Private	17	09	Baltimore, MD
10	Columbia University	Private	18	10	New York, NY
11	University of Pennsylvania	Private	19	11	Philadelphia, PA
12	Duke University	Private	21	12	Durham, NC
13	University of Michigan	Public	21	12	Ann Arbor, MI
14	University of California--Berkeley	Public	27	14	Berkeley, CA
15	Northwestern University	Private	28	15	Evanston, IL

16	University of California--Los Angeles	Public	33	16	Los Angeles, CA
17	University of California	Public	38	17	San Diego
18	Carnegie Mellon University	Private	47	18	Pittsburgh, PA
19	New York University	Private	52	19	New York, NY
20	Brown University	Private	53	20	Providence, RI

During last two decades, Indian government realized the need of additional Universities in the country to provide higher education to all young aspirants and promoted the private University model in the country with the reason that establishment of Private universities is the best solution to this problem in the country without financial burden to the government. Accordingly, based on section 22 of UGC act, the Indian government has allowed the state governments to establish private universities in the respective states. Consequently, 22 states in the country have established private universities and as per UGC information, presently 264 private universities established in the country are competent to award degrees with the approval of the statutory councils, wherever required through their main campus (Table 2). Accordingly, many established private universities in different states of the country have started their higher educational service and formulating their strategies to provide quality and innovative education to attract many students in the areas of high demand in the industry and society. Due to non-availability of any financial support from the state and central governments, private universities are trying to sustain through their only strategy of service differentiation through 21st century curriculum and industry integrated programme design. A good number of research studies are carried out on challenges and opportunities for private universities in India [2 -10]. In this paper, we have studied the activities of private universities in India which include a number of Private universities in different states of the country, strategies of private universities in terms of their infrastructure, a variety of courses, fee structure of various courses, innovative curriculum, quality education through quality faculty, research investments, research promotions and research output, industry & other institutes collaborations, foreign university & institutes collaboration, placement services, student involvement of research, and innovation & best practices [11-25].

Table 2 : Composition of various types of Universities in India as on 05/06/2017

S. No.	University Type	Number	Percentage
1	Central Universities	46	5.8%
2	State Universities	359	45.3%
3	Deemed Universities	123	15.6%
4	Private Universities	264	33.3%
	Total	792	100 %

2. Research Objectives :

The objectives of this study are :

- (1) To know about establishment and distribution of private universities in different states of the country.
- (2) Comparison of Private universities in terms of their age, land, and their number of faculty departments.
- (3) The position grabbed by Private universities in NIRF best university ranking based on various NIRF overall parameters strengths.
- (4) List of private universities included in NIRF-2017 Best Management Institution ranking.
- (5) To study Fee charging strategies of these Universities like Low-fees low-cost strategy, High-fees high-quality strategy, and Nominal-fees High-quality strategy etc.
- (6) To know Private universities having Medical Courses including MBBS.
- (7) Study on innovative curriculum, quality education through quality faculty, research investments, research promotions and research output, industry & other institutes collaborations, foreign university & institutes collaboration, placement services, student involvement in research, and innovation & best practices.
- (8) Advantages of innovations and best practices offered by Private Universities for students.
- (9) Recommendations to the private universities for improving their performance based on observations to improve the quality, relevancy, and effectiveness of educational services and research contributions.

The data are collected from UGC official website and the official websites of the private universities and the fee structure and other data are mentioned in this paper for the academic year 2017-18. Some of the fee-related data are obtained by personally calling the universities using the telephone numbers mentioned in respective universities websites.

3. Private Universities in different states in India :

Even though 264 private universities are established in the country through various state government acts, only a few universities could able to establish required infrastructure. As per the survey and the data depicted in table 3, out of 264 private universities established by the year 2017, 90 of them are started before 2010 and remaining are started after 2010. Except few, most of the private universities are now in developing stage and due to heavy competition between public and private universities, are struggling to establish mainly due to financial constraints. Since the investments required on land,

infrastructure, and faculty is very high and return on investment is very slow due to heavy competition by government-funded public universities.

Table 3 : Number of Private Universities, States wise started before and after 2010.

S. No	State	No. of Private Universities	Started before 2010	Started after 2010
1	Arunachal Pradesh	7	0	7
2	Assam	5	2	3
3	Chhattisgarh	9	1	8
4	Gujarat	27	10	17
5	Haryana	19	4	15
6	Himachal Pradesh	17	9	8
7	Jharkhand	8	1	7
8	Karnataka	12	2	10
9	Madhya Pradesh	23	4	19
10	Maharashtra	6	0	6
11	Manipur	1	0	1
12	Meghalaya	8	6	2
13	Mizoram	1	1	0
14	Nagaland	2	2	0
15	Orissa	6	2	4
16	Punjab	14	3	11
17	Rajasthan	30	18	12

18	Sikkim	5	4	1
19	Uttarakhand	11	5	6
20	Uttar Pradesh	28	15	13
21	Tripura	1	1	0
22	West Bengal	8	0	8
Total			90	158

4. Comparison of Private Universities in terms of Age, Land, and Faculties :

The private universities which are funded and managed by financially powerful NGO or by sustained profit-making companies are able to grow at a faster pace. Like in other industrial and service sector, private universities in India follows either 'Low-fee – low-cost strategy', 'High-fee – high-quality strategy', or 'Low-fee – high-quality strategy'.

Table 4 : List of some selected Private Universities based on their age, infrastructure, and the number of faculty/departments established.

S. No	State	No. of Private Universities	Year of Start /UGC Letter	Land in Acres	No of Faculty/Dept.
1	Arunachal Pradesh	1. Indira Gandhi Technological and Medical Science University	2012	83.5	03
2	Assam	1. Don Bosco University	2008	500	04
3	Chhattisgarh	1. CV Raman University	2006	48	11
4	Gujarat	1. Dhirubhai Ambani Institute of Information and Communication Technology	2003/2004	50	01
		2. Nirma University	2003/2004	115	10
		3. Parul University	2003	150	20
5	Haryana	1. AMITY University, Gurgaon	2010/2010	110	23
		2. O.P. Jindal Global University	2009/2009	80	06
		3. SRM University, Haryana	2013/2014	48	19

		4. G.D. Goenka University, Haryana	2013/2013	60	10
6	Himachal Pradesh	1. Jaypee University of Information Technology, Himachal Pradesh	2002/2002	25	9
		2. Chitkara University, Himachal Pradesh	2009/2009	17	4
7	Jharkhand	1. The Institute of Chartered Financial Analysts of India University, Jharkhand	2008/2009	6.8	2
8	Karnataka	1. Alliance University	2010	40	5
		2. PES University	2013	25	9
		3. CMR University	2013	60	8
		4. Ajim Premji University	2010	12	3
		5. Reva University	2013	43	6
		6. M. S. Ramaya University	2013	76	7
		7. Srinivas University	2013	45	8
9	Madhya Pradesh	Amity University	2010	100	12
		Jagran Lakecity University, Bhopal	2013	200	11
10	Maharashtra	Amity University	2014	1200	21
11	Orissa	Xevier University	2013	37	07
12	Punjab	1. Lovely Professional University	2005	600	60
		2. Sri Guru Granth Sahib World University	2008	136.75	12
13	Rajasthan	1. Amity University	2008	152	21
		2. Manipal University	2011	600	14

		3. Jaipur National University	2007	120	17
14	Sikkim	1. Sikkim Manipal University	1995	33	11
15	Uttarakhand	1. University of Petroleum and Energy Studies	2003	42	07
		2. Himgiri Zee University	2003	50	05
16	Uttar Pradesh	1. AMITY University	2003	110	19
		2. Bennett University	2016	68	06
		3. Sharda University	2009	63	13
		4. Jaypee University	2001	25	09
		5. Teerthanker Mahaveer University	2008	140	17
		6. Noida International University	2010	75	08
		7. Golgotias University	1999	52	18

5. Private Universities in NIRF Ranking :

National Institutional Ranking Framework (NIRF) is an Indian government higher educational institutions ranking agency approved by MHRD, The ranking framework proposed a methodology to rank higher educational institutions including Universities across the country. This methodology consists of five parameters for ranking which include (1) Teaching, Learning and Resources, (2) Research and Professional Practices, (3) Graduation Outcomes, (4) Outreach and Inclusivity, and (5) Public perception. The list of private universities included in NIRF-2017 in best universities ranking is listed in Table 5. Only 17 private universities could find a Top ranking position out of 200 Top universities. List of private universities included in NIRF-2017 under best Management Institutions ranking is listed in Table 5. Surprisingly only four management institutions under private universities could secure top ranking out of Top 100 Management institutions (Source : <https://www.nirfindia.org/ranking2017.html>).

Table 5 : List of private universities included in NIRF-2017 Best university ranking.

S. No.	Name of the University	NIRF Rank	Overall Parameter Based Strength
1	Amity University, Uttara Pradesh	52	39.17 %

2	Shiv Nadar University, Uttara Pradesh	60	37.95 %
3	Nirma University, Ahmedabad, Gujrath	75	36.21 %
4	Jaypee University, Noida, Uttara Pradesh	81	35.69 %
5	Jaypee University of Information Technology, Himachal Pradesh	93	34.11 %
6	PES University, Karnataka	94	33.94 %
7	Chitkara University	111	-
8	Dhirubhai Ambani Institute of Information and Communication Technology, Gujrath	114	-
9	Sikkim Manipal University, Sikkim	139	-
10	University of Petroleum and Energy Studies, Uttarakhand	145	-
11	Assam Don Bosco University, Assam	152	-
12	Dr. C.V. Raman University, Chhattisgarh	167	-
13	Ganpat University, Gujarat	170	-
14	Manav Rachna International University, Haryana	180	-
15	Manipal University, Rajasthan	181	-
16	Sharda University, Uttar Pradesh	189	-
17	Teerthanker Mahaveer University, Uttar Pradesh	193	-

Table 6 : List of private universities included in NIRF-2017 Best Management Institution ranking

S. No.	Name of the University	Rank (100)	Parameter Based Strength
1	Nirma University	31	45.81 %
2	Xavier University	33	44.85 %
3	Integral University	82	-

4	PES University	92	-
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6. Fee Charging Strategy of Indian Private Universities :

Since private universities are self financing institutions, their annual revenue is mainly dependent on their fee collection strategy by offering innovative futuristic and demand based courses. Depending upon the location, infrastructure, quality, innovation, and placement service provided, private universities collect a different amount of annual course fees. Based on observation on fee collection for different courses, the fee-charging strategy of private universities can be divided into Low fees-low cost strategy, High cost-high quality strategy, and Nominal fees-High quality strategy.

6.1 Low Fees – Low cost Strategy :

Many private universities follow low-fees and low-cost strategy as listed in Table 7. This is mainly due to the heavy competition from Public Universities in neighbourhood. Some of the private universities which have substantially low infrastructure also follow this strategy to attract students of low income background. Such programmes usually contain less innovations in terms of value additions, quality of infrastructure, and academic vigorous. Private universities like Techno Global University of Meghalaya, Integral University of Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh, Singhania University of Rajasthan, and Monad University of Uttar Pradesh, and MATS University of Raipur, Chhattisgarh, are charging less than Rs. 50,000 for B.Tech programmes annually. Similarly, the Universities like Dr. C.V. Raman University of Bilaspur, Chhattisgarh, Kadi Sarva Vishwavidyalaya of Gujarat, Techno Global University of Meghalaya, The Global Open University of Nagaland, Shri Jagdish Prasad Jhabarmal Tibrewala University of Rajasthan, Monad University of Uttar Pradesh, Singhania University of Rajasthan are charging less than Rs. 50,000 as an annual fee for MBA programmes.

Table 7 : List of Private Universities started before 2010 which follow Low Fee – Low cost strategy

S.No	Name of the Private University	Annual Fee for B.E/B.Tech	Annual Fee for MBA
1	Assam Down Town University	70,000	1,25,000
2	Dr. C.V. Raman University	nil	51,500
3	Mats University	30,000	70,000
4	Ganpat University	87,000	81,000
5	Kadi Sarva Vishwavidyalaya	nil	42,000
6	Manav Bharti University	82,500	75,000
7	Indus International University	94,500	1,10,000

8	The Institute Of Chartered Financial Analyst Of India University	87,500	1,15,500
9	CMJ University	50,000	60,000
10	Techno Global University	36,000	30,000
11	The Global Open University	nil	14,462
12	Sri Guru Granth Sahib World University	86,000	86,000
13	Bhagawath University	61,000	60,000
14	Dr K.N. Modi University	94,900	95,800
15	Jaythi Vidyapeeth Women's University	90,000	90,000
16	Jodhpur National University	90,000	68,000
17	Mahatma Jyoti Rao Phoole University	71,000	61,000
18	Mewar University	88,000	78,000
19	NIMS University	66,500	75,000
20	Shri Jagdish Prasad Jhabarmal Tibrewala University	70,000	50,000
21	Shridhar University	83,000	87,000
22	Singhania University	41,000	41,300
23	Integral University	35,000	50,000
24	Mohammad Ali Jauhar University	69,000	55,000
25	Monad University	21,300	48,600
26	Shri Venkateshwara University	70,000	65,000
27	Swami Vivekanand Subharti University	75,000	1,00,000
28	Himgiri Zee University	85,000	1,50,000

The Private universities with a low-fee- low-cost strategy provide education at a minimal cost to the student. Their main aim is to provide basic and normal education at minimum cost so that it can reach

to the people. Table 7 includes private universities who offer B.Tech programme for an annual fee below Rs. 1,00,000 and MBA programme annual fee below Rs. 1,50,000.

6.2 High Fees –High Quality Strategy :

Some of the private universities started before the year 2010 also follow High-Fee – High-quality strategy as shown in Table 8. The Table 8 depicts only the sample fees charged by such universities for their B.Tech. and MBA programmes. It is found that so many universities, Alliance University of Bangalore, Nirma University of Gujarat, O.P. Jindal Global University of Haryana, and University of Petroleum and Energy Studies of Uttarakhand are charging more than Rs. 5,00,000 annual fee for MBA programme and Sikkim-Manipal University of Sikkim, Sharda University of Uttar Pradesh, University of Petroleum and Energy Studies of Uttarakhand, G.D. Goenka University of Haryana, and PES University Bangalore are charging more than Rs. 2,00,000 annually for their B.Tech. Programmes. These universities have differentiated themselves either through their brand image which has been built from intensive quality initiatives from a long time, or massive infrastructure, or Training through foreign faculty members, or through one semester abroad, or offering high tech elective papers through industry tie-up etc. The table 8 lists only the universities who charge an annual fee of Rs. 1,50,000 and above for their B.Tech programme and an annual fee of Rs. 2,50,000 and above for their MBA programme.

Table 8 : List of universities started before 2010 which follow ‘High cost – High quality’ Strategies

S.No	Name of the Universities	Annual Fee for B.Tech	Annual fee for MBA
1	Alliance University	1,80,000	6,75,000
2	Nirma University	1,57,725	5,46,000
3	O.P. Jindal Global University	-	5,50,000
4	Amity University, MP	1,50,000	2,77,075
5	Lovely Professional University	1,89,000	2,50,000
6	Amity University, Rajasthan	1,55,000	2,62,000
7	Sikkim- Manipal University	2,42,000	2,70,000
8	Amity University UP	1,85,000	4,27,000
9	Sharda University	2,05,000	2,50,000
10	University of Petroleum and Energy Studies	3,37,500	5,57,000

11	G.D Goenka University, Haryana	2,15,000	3,95,000
12	PES University, Bangalore	3,00,000	4,00,000
13	Jaypee University of Information Technology	1,82,500	Nil

6.3 Nominal Fees – High-Quality Strategy :

Apart from the conventional strategies of low-fee low quality, and high-fee – high-quality, there are some philanthropic private universities charges low fees for bright students without compromising high quality. Some of the private universities which follow such strategy are listed in Table 9 with a sample of annual fees charged for their B.Tech. and MBA programmes. Many of private universities in Table 9 charges nearly Rs. 1,00,000 for B.Tech programmes and between Rs. 1,00,000 to Rs. 2,00,000 for MBA programmes. Many of these universities are financially supported by either Charitable Trust or through public donations and contributions. Table 9 includes private universities who have quality education for a nominal fee. Nominal fee falls under the category of Rs.1,00,000 to Rs.2,50,000 which is decent fee structure and affordable for many of the students. These are the universities which are offering good quality education with nominal fees and are established on or before 2010 and reached many students all over the world by their quality, commitment, and fee structure.

Table 9 : List of universities started before 2010 which follow 'Nominal Fees – Highly Quality Strategies'

S.No	Name of the Private University	Annual Fee for B.E/B.tech	Annual Fee for MBA
1	Assam Don Bosco University	1,36,000	1,90,500
2	Ahmadabad University	1,07,500	1,29,250
3	Charotar University Of Science And Technology	1,35,000	1,35,000
4	Dhirubhai Ambani Institute Of Information And Communication Technology	1,35,000	Nil
5	Navrachana University	1,15,000	1,50,000
6	Apeejay Stya University	1,64,200	2,16,200
7	Chitkara University	1,54,000	2,23,000
8	The Institute Of Chatered Financial Analyst Of India University	Nil	1,02,000

9	Jaypee University Of Engineering And Technology	1,87,500	Nil
10	The Institute Of Chatered Financial Analyst Of India University	-	1,07,000
11	Jagannath University	1,06,000	1,83,000
12	Jaipur National University	1,30,000	1,30,000
13	G.L.A. University	1,58,250	1,58,000
14	SRM University, Haryana	2,16,000	1,68,000

6.4. Private Universities with Medical Courses :

Some of the private universities have started medical courses at undergraduate and postgraduate level. The financial status and hence the investment abilities of such universities are considered to be high improving and growing in terms of their infrastructure at a faster pace. Table 10 contains the list of private universities which offers medical and Paramedical courses at undergraduate and postgraduate level.

Table 10 : List of Private Universities started before 2010 having Medical Courses including MBBS

S.No	Name of the Private University	Annual Fee for MBBS	B.TECH	MBA
1	Maharishi Markandeshwar University	5,00,000	80,000	70,000
2	Sikkim- Manipal University	12,20,000	2,42,000	2,70,000
3	Integral University	15,00,000	35,000	50,000
4	Sharda University	11,40,000	2,05,000	2,50,000
5	Swami Vivekanand Subharti University	9,35,500	75,000	1,00,000
6	Teerthanker Mahaveer University	16,70,000	1,28,600	1,59,200

The above-mentioned table shows the universities having MBBS course along with B.Tech and MBA established on or before 2010 in India with low fee-low cost strategy and High fee- quality education strategy.

7. Advantages for Private Universities for Innovations & Best Practices :

Irrespective of financial constraints and lack of support from the government for infrastructure, the recently started private universities in India are doing exceptionally good in terms of designing and

offering innovative industry-oriented customized programmes to their students. By designing super-specialized and customized programmes private universities are attracting students for quality education. Some of the observed innovations of private universities are listed in Table 11.

Table 11 : Advantages of innovations and best practices offered by Private universities for students

S. No.	Innovation	Advantages to Students
1	Providing laptop to the students	Improve the technical aspects and also platform to gather knowledge.
2	Classrooms with LCD	Pictorial examples and easy understanding.
3	College website or app	Updated attendance and syllabus material which can be uploaded by teacher can be downloaded by students
4	Open book examination	Improve the knowledge of the students in application based questions
5	Online submission of assignments	Make students punctual in submission.
6	Online examination	Examination conducted on the system in order save time and waste of paper and also make correction easier.
7	Result	Published through college application which helps the students to know individual results on their account.
8	Online Open education	It helps students from anywhere and anybody to avail education.
9	Choice Based Credit System	Students can choose the subjects as per their preference to earn required credit.
10	Competency-based Credit System	Students have to earn required competency to pass a subject or degree. There is no fixed time frame to complete a course. Students may have their own pace of learning.
11	Continuous assessment examination system	Assessments in the form of exams are spread over the course instead of course end exam only. Students have no pressure to remember the entire semester or year curriculum during the final exam.
12	Dual Degree Programmes	Students can register two courses simultaneously and get graduation in both areas. This allows them to utilize their time

		effectively to earn multiple degrees.
13	Student Exchange Programs	Through exchange of a group of students between different cultures/social environment, students can get exposure and learn to become a better decision maker.
14	Semester Abroad System	Wide exposure and skill development leading to the enhanced job opportunity.
15	Earn while learn model	Students get working experience, enhanced participation and responsibility in the classroom, and realize the value for money.

8. Recommendations :

The following recommendations are proposed based on observations and analysis of private universities admission, service, research, and annual fee strategies.

1. Private universities should focus on providing high-quality education to the students at affordable cost.
2. Private universities should focus on creating innovators by adding research components in their curriculum.
3. Private universities should use the autonomy given to them effectively to continuously update their curriculum which is not possible for public sector universities due to lengthy bureaucratic procedures involved in the approval process.
4. Investment in infrastructure and providing awesome facilities will allow the private universities to follow high-fee high-quality strategy still will be able to attract more students.
5. Innovations discussed in Table 11 will give competitive advantages to private universities to improve their brand image.
6. Private universities with medical courses at the undergraduate and postgraduate level will be able to follow low fee but the high-quality strategy in non-medical courses due to their financial ability to invest more to improve the infrastructure.
7. Private universities should focus on research and publications along with forming the strategy to creating academic Excellency like top private universities in the USA.
8. Private universities in India also follow the path of Top Private Research universities in the USA by following a strategy of not for profit slogan and attracting highly qualified faculty members from all around the country and abroad.
9. Private universities should focus on the involvement of undergraduate and postgraduate students in research by adding one or more research-based subjects in the curriculum and compulsory publications as necessary requirements for awarding degrees.
10. Private universities which have started many programmes under several faculties as shown in Table 4 can serve more people in the society by offering higher education in wider and specialized areas. This will also contribute to the country through added multi-disciplinary research and publications in many fields.
11. Private universities should also focus their innovative strategy on various parameters of NIRF Ranking of the country. Focus on faculty developments, appointing research background faculties with research degrees and proven research and publication records, encouraging faculty members for active research by setting up university funded research centres, appointing star achievers in research as role-models for young researcher gives added advantage to establish name and fame to attract global students to the universities.

12. Offering super specialization courses with industry involvement allows universities to follow high fee high-quality strategy and still attracts many students.
13. It trains the students by providing the best quality teacher and facilities which is available.
14. They also try to improve the quality of their working by introducing new ideas in order to be the best among other private universities.
15. Continuous innovation and brand building by globalizing the student admission and faculty recruitments will improve the societal perspective of the universities.
16. Offering dual degree programmes to the students both at under graduation and post graduation level will be more attractive due to the reason that students get the opportunity to become multi-disciplinary experts without wasting valuable time in their young period of life.

Since the private universities have a comparative advantage with autonomy to make innovations, they can grow and establish as an effective university and institution of eminence in a short time. As time progress, there will be many private universities in better NIRF ranking umbrella with the improved parameter based performance which is presently low as seen in Tables 5 & 6.

9. Conclusion :

The study focuses on identifying state-wise private universities in India, separating age based performance, and faculties expansion strategies in private universities, private universities identified under NIRF ranking and their parameter based performance, annual fee charging strategy followed by different private universities in India. It also helps to understand which all universities provide their maximum quality services to their students. We have also studied the performance scores given by NIRF, MHRD, Govt. of India for various criterions like Teaching, Learning & Resources, Research and Professional Practice, Graduation Outcomes, Outreach and Inclusivity, Public Perception. It is found that only few private universities till now found place in NIRF ranking and there is ample scope to progress further through effective completion in terms of quality improvement both at academic performance and research output. It is seen that private universities in India follow various strategies to face the competition and attract students for different courses. This includes low-fee low-quality strategy, Low-fee high-quality strategy, and High-fee High-quality strategy. The paper also identified various quality strategies followed by Indian old private universities (started on or before 2010) to charge low, average and high annual fees for their B.Tech and MBA programmes. Many innovative strategies followed by these universities to attract more students are also identified and listed.

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